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UNESCO CREATIVE CITIES NETWORK AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY AND TOURISM IN AZERBAIJAN (IN THE CONTEXT OF MUSEOLOGY)

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Abstract

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) are taking initiatives in various fields. One of these initiatives is the creation of the UNESCO Creative Cities Network. Three cities of Azerbaijan have been included in the UNESCO Creative Cities Network. In 2017, Sheki was included in the list of creative cities (the theme “Crafts and Folk Art”), in 2019 – Baku (the theme “Design”), and in 2021 – Lankaran (the theme “Gastronomy”). The inclusion in the future of our other cities in similar lists in the relevant industries will contribute to the comprehensive recognition of the republic on an international scale, and the establishment of broad ties in relevant areas, and the development in the country of various types of tourism, the creative economy and the knowledge society as a whole.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, knowledge society, creative economy, tourism, culture, art, museums.

Introduction. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has taken various initiatives in the relevant fields. One of them is the creation of the UNESCO Creative Cities Network (UCCN), in which the cities included in the network should share their experience and develop partnership relations with the participation of public and private sectors, as well as civil society. The network was founded in 2004 to collaborate with cities that identify creativity as a strategic factor for sustainable development. Currently, the cities included in the network are working to make creative and cultural industries the main focus of their development plans at the local level and to actively cooperate at the international level.

World Cities Day is celebrated on October 31 every year since 2014. This holiday was established by the decision of the UN General Assembly held in December 2013 in order to focus the attention of the international community on the problems of urbanization and solving the relevant issues to ensure the sustainable development of cities around the world.

It is no secret that the socio-economic development of every city depends on a number of factors. The safety and comfort of the city population, the environmental situation, the creation of the necessary infrastructure, the quality of the provided services, etc. – all these factors are characterize cities. According to the UN, more than half of the world's population currently lives in cities. In 2050, this number will increase to 68%. For comparison, let's say that at the beginning of the 19th century, only 2% of the population lived in cities, and in 1950, 30% [8]. The increase in the number of urban population creates a number of problems in the field of security and sustainable development.

In 2015, the member countries of the UN adopted 17 goals leading to sustainable development within the framework of the “The Global Goals and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development”. These goals are 1) no poverty and 2) zero hunger, 3) good health and well-being, 4) quality education, 5) gender equality, 6)

clean water and sanitation, 7) affordable and clean energy, 8) decent work and economic growth, 9) industry, innovation and infrastructure, 10) reducing inequalities, 11) sustainable cities and communities, 12) responsible consumption and production, 13) climate action, 14) life below water, 15) life on land, 16) peace, justice and strong institutions and 17) partnerships [18].

If we look at the set goals, it is clear that the points listed above are reflected in all areas, including the development of cities. Therefore, the UNESCO Creative Cities Network initiative is particularly relevant for our time. It is no coincidence that the new cities included in the network are announced every two years on the eve of World Cities Day.

The place of UCCN in the development of tourism and creative economy. As noted by economists, “countries in the global world attach special importance to the development of exports in order to maintain their economic well-being and achieve sustainable economic growth... specializing in exports of limited products harms the country's economy with fluctuations in the world market. Therefore, there is a need for countries to expand their basket of export products” [5, p. 28].

Taking into account modern realities, tourism products must be included in this basket. Currently, tourism occupies an important place in inter-country relations. The reason for this is the expansion of mutual relations in economy, scientific-cultural integration, scientific-technical progress and other directions. According to scientists, tourism, especially cultural tourism, expands economic, social, cultural, scientific-technical relations between different countries, and also plays an important role in maintaining mutual trust, peace, and strengthening mutual friendly relations [6, p. 3].

The activity of UCCN is the expansion of cultural initiatives, the creation, production and distribution of cultural products and services, the development of creativity and innovation centers, the creation of opportunities for people working in the field of culture, the accessibility of cultural life, the participation of everyone

in these initiatives, including marginalized and disabled citizens. Activity, in short, is aimed at the integration of culture and creativity into sustainable development plans.

Created in 2004 and covering up to 350 cities of the world, UNESCO's Creative Cities Network promotes international cooperation among the world's cities. The cities included in the network are innovative and strategically important, they come up with large-scale initiatives that have a positive economic, social, cultural and environmental impact, thereby supporting the aforementioned "The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development" [13].

The network covers a range of creative fields: crafts and folk art, media art, cinema, design, gastronomy, literature and music. These listed are areas aimed at the development of various types of tourism and creative economy, along with a number of directions. Thus, through various projects, intercity cooperation in relevant areas is established, knowledge and experience are exchanged. Also, the network ensures the flow of tourists to these places by engaging in extensive promotion of those cities. On the other hand, initiatives aimed at the development of various creative fields accelerate the development of the creative economy as a whole, and contribute to the improvement of the well-being of the city population by attracting additional income.

Development of knowledge society and tourism in Azerbaijan as one of the priority issues. A number of legal documents regulate the field of tourism in our country. For example, the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Tourism" (December 27, 2021), "Strategic Roadmap for the Development of the Specialized Tourism Industry in the Republic of Azerbaijan" (December 6, 2016), "Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities for Socio-Economic Development" (February 2, 2021) and based on this document "Socio-economic development strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2022-2026" (July 22, 2022), etc.

In the "Strategic Roadmap for the Development of the Specialized Tourism Industry in the Republic of Azerbaijan", it is noted that the development of tourism mainly affects three areas – the Gross Domestic Product, increasing employment and the socio-economic development of the regions, and the development of the infrastructure of the regions. In addition, the tourism sector supports efforts in the direction of environmental sustainability, cultural heritage, protection and development of local values. A successful tourism strategy helps to improve the country's image internationally, so tourism also acts as a marketing tool for countries [1, p. 8].

If we look at the "Socio-economic development strategy for 2022-2026", one of the main directions of activity of the national economy of Azerbaijan is the strengthening of strategic, institutional and financial mechanisms to ensure sustainable development of the tourism sector. This direction includes the preparation and implementation of state programs for the development of tourism, the implementation of a marketing and communication plan for expanding the country's tour-

ism potential, the creation of a mechanism for coordinating the activities of participants in the tourism industry in the form of regular dialogue, as well as the implementation of other projects and measures [2].

Taking into account the above legal documents, we can come to the conclusion that our republic attaches great importance to the development of sustainable and socially responsible tourism. The goal of sustainable tourism is to organize more efficient and humane activities based on the interests of local communities and environmental opportunities. During sustainable tourism services are based on the socio-economic and ecological opportunities of the area, these opportunities determine the characteristics of tourism activities, travelers behave in accordance with the culture of the places they come to, respect natural objects, customs and traditions, establish a relationship with the local population on the basis of friendship and mutual respect [10].

Socially responsible tourism also gives a person the opportunity to make a real contribution to the sustainable development of the place he travels to. Socially responsible tourism ensures the protection of nature, promotes the social and economic development of the region, instills a sense of respect for the historical-cultural heritage, the environment and traditions [11, p. 13].

Summarizing what has been mentioned, let us note that the creation of tourism products in accordance with the requirements of the modern era will give a great boost to the development of the creative economy in our country.

Prospects of Azerbaijan's representation in UNESCO's Creative Cities network. To date, 3 cities of Azerbaijan have been included in the network. In 2017, the city of Shaki was included in the network's list of creative cities on the theme of "crafts and folk art", in 2019, the city of Baku was included in the list of "design", and in 2021, the city of Lankaran was included in the list of creative cities on the theme of "gastronomy". On the official website of UCCN, information reflecting the specifics and future priorities of each city in the creative field is posted.

In Shaki, which is known as the place of many types of crafts and folk arts, especially netting, pottery and sericulture, the following initiatives are planned for future activities: a) development and implementation of a comprehensive marketing program for the development of local creativity, the production and distribution of handicrafts and folk art products; b) establishment of the Shaki Institute of Arts and Crafts, turning this place into a center of professional education in the field of craft technologies, entrepreneurship, management and marketing skills in the field of creativity and innovation; c) developing a multifaceted cultural tourism strategy aimed at making art workshops accessible to everyone, especially people with limited opportunities; d) organization of International Shaki craft and folk art fair twice a year in order to strengthen partnership with other creative cities; e) management of a regional network of cities in Turkic-speaking countries to stimulate the integration of craft and folk art sectors into local development plans; f) feasibility studies of projects

aimed at exploring new potential cultural tourism routes connecting Sheki with other UCCN cities in the field of crafts and folk art, gastronomy and music [17].

Known as the center of innovative projects and start-ups in the field of design, **Baku** offers wide opportunities in the field of fashion, graphic and web design, eco-design, architecture, interior design and urban landscape. The following initiatives are planned to be implemented in Baku in the future: a) creation of opportunities for authors working in various design fields; b) improving opportunities for authors at various levels and opening jobs for them; c) providing support for the production, distribution and dissemination of products and services in the field of design; d) strengthening relations with other creative fields such as crafts and folk art, gastronomy and music covered by the network; e) expansion of cooperation with creative cities that consider design and other creative fields as an important factor of sustainable urban development [14].

With its rich agricultural potential, historical and cultural heritage, **Lankaran** makes important contributions to the non-oil economy. The following steps are envisaged for Lankaran: a) expansion of opportunities for creation, production, distribution and distribution of products and services in the field of gastronomy; b) strengthening synergies with other creative field covered by the UNESCO Creative Cities Network, such as crafts and folk art and design; c) expansion of cooperation between cities that see gastronomy and other related creative fields as a strategic driving force of urban development; d) creating wider opportunities for students, authors, experts and civil society to exchange knowledge and experience [16].

Of course, in the future, the inclusion of other cities of our country in such lists according to various topics will promote both the comprehensive recognition of the republic in the international world, the establishment of extensive relations in relevant fields, and the development of various types of tourism, creative economy and knowledge society in the country. For example, taking into account the colorful and rich culinary culture of Azerbaijan, various cities of the republic can be included in the list of creative cities on the theme of “gastronomy”, Shemakha – on the theme of “literature”, Shusha – on the theme of “music”, etc. In addition, taking into account films shot in Baku, the city can be included on the theme of “cinema”, in accordance with projects on media art – on the theme “media art”, taking into account the major music festivals held in Gabala and the role of these festivals in music tourism, the city of Gabala can be included in the network on the theme “music”, etc.

Now extensive repair and reconstruction works are being carried out in Karabakh. As experts have noted, “the creative economy to be formed in the Karabakh economic region is important in providing employment, increasing the volume of creative goods and services in exports, and achieving sustainable economic growth... The transition from culture to economy, the creation of cultural and creative sectors will also stimulate the development of tourism” [7, p. 172].

Much can be said about Shusha's role in the development of the musical culture of Azerbaijan. Academician Zemfira Safarova, who covered this issue extensively, writes that “there are several cities in the world where music is absorbed into every stone, every castle, and its entire aura. This is Vienna in Austria, Naples in Italy, and Shusha in Karabakh” [12, p. 3].

Indeed, it is enough to list only some of the outstanding musical figures who came out of Shusha, for example, wonderful musicians and singers Bulbul, Sadigjan, Jabbar Garyagyoglu, Mir Mohsun Navvab, Khan Shushinsky, Zulfi Adigozalov, Gurban Pirimov, our famous composers Uzeyir Hajibeyli, Fikret Amirov, Niyazi, Zulfugar Hajibeyov, Afrasiyab Badalbeyli, Suleiman Aleskerov, Vasif Adigozalov and others to prove that Shusha is the musical cradle of Azerbaijan. Therefore, the inclusion of Shusha in the UCCN on the theme “music” is one of the priority issues facing us, and the necessary measures are being taken in this direction.

Speaking about Shamakhi, we should list some figures of Azerbaijani literature, for example, Imadeddin Nasimi, Khagani Shirvani, Mirza Alekper Sabir, Seyid Azim Shirvani, Sultan Ganizadeh, Muhammad Hadi, Abbas Sahhat and many others, in order to recognize the validity of our proposal to include Shamakhi in the UNESCO Creative Cities Network on the theme “literature”. The same applies to our other offers.

UCCN and museums. It is known that tourists who come to different cities go to the museums operating here, along with other places. In general, the expansion of museum functions, the active participation of these institutions in the life of modern societies, the direct participation of museums in both the collection and creation of knowledge create ample opportunities for close contact of these institutions with creative industries.

In our opinion, full information about cities can be conveyed to visitors through museums of history of cities, which are still quite rare in Azerbaijan. When talking about museums of history of cities, it should be noted that everything surrounding these institutions is the subject of their research. Museums of cities convey the culture of city residents to the audience, promote the uniqueness of communities, and engage in activities aimed at the cultural development of communities. All the areas we have listed coincide with the goals of the UNESCO Creative Cities Network, such museums occupy an important place both in the development of the creative economy, in the education of people, and in the wider recognition of cities in the world.

We got information about only two museums of history of cities currently operating in Azerbaijan. These are the museums of the cities of Sumgait and Mingachevir, which were created in the 60-s of the 20th century. At that time, such a museum was also established in Shusha, but it operated for a short time.

We have prepared and presented to the public the initial concepts of the museums of Baku [3], Shusha [15] and Nakhchivan [9].

Taking into account one of the priority issues for inclusion in the UCCN, let us state that in addition to

two music profile museums in Shusha – Bulbul and Uzeyir Hajibeyli's house museums, the houses of a number of our musical figures are recognized as cultural monuments. We have presented the initial concept of the house-museum of Jabbar Garyagdioglu, which is aimed at the development of music tourism in Shusha [4].

In our opinion, the implementation of such projects and the creation of relevant museums will give a great impetus to the development of creative industries in the republic.

Conclusion and offers. Thus, the goals of the UCCN are realized through the exchange of knowledge and experience both at the level of the network's member cities and at the international level, through pilot projects bringing together public, private sectors and civil societies, partnerships and initiatives, programs of professional and creative exchange, events, aimed at sustainable urban development, coordination, propaganda, etc. Our cities have rich potential to tap into this network in various creative fields, and we must use this potential to promote relevant projects. We also consider the creation of various types of museums, especially museums of history of cities, to be a pressing issue within the UCCN.

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